

THE INFLUENCE OF MAGICAL FAIRY TALES ON CHILDREN'S PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract

Opinions of scientists about the positive and negative effects of magical fairy tales on children's psychology. At the same time, about the occurrence of distortions in their views on life. Forming the skill of choosing a fairy tale by studying the child's age and mentality when choosing fairy tales.

Keywords: Influence, magical fairy tales, stereotypes, aggression, materialism, violence, death, evil, gender roles fear, anxiety, emotional state, adaptation

Kalit so'zlar: Ta'sir, sehri ertaklar, stereotiplar, tajovuzkorlik, materializm, zo'ravonlik, o'lim, yovuzlik, gender rollari qo'rquv, tashvish, hissiy holat, moslashish.

Ключевые слова: Влияние, волшебные сказки, стереотипы, агрессия, материализм, насилие, смерть, зло, гендерные роли, страх, тревожность, эмоциональное состояние, адаптация

Introduction

Children are told by their parents and grandparents different fairy tales from their youth. This had a sufficiently positive effect on the formation of their impressions and their vocabulary. Their abilities develop significantly. But it can have the opposite effect on their emotional state. Because magical fairy tales are far from reality. As a result, as children grow up, they cannot accept that there is no magic in real life, that no fairies will come to their aid in difficult times, and that problems cannot be solved by themselves.

Some scientists says that after learning the good side of fairy tales: " Fairy tales are vital to the mind of a child because it allows them to see different morals and meanings of the world, even if they don't understand these ideas at the time that they learn them. In essence, the impact of fairy tales lies in their ability to touch our hearts and minds, igniting emotions that remind us of the beauty of the human experience. They whisper that no matter how old we grow, the magic of imagination and the depth of our emotions remain vibrant and alive ". The above points are about general fairy tales.

Methods

Here are a few potential drawbacks:

1. Unrealistic Expectations: Fairy tales often present idealized versions of reality, where problems are easily solved and happy endings are guaranteed. This can lead to unrealistic expectations in children, making them feel disappointed or disillusioned when faced with the challenges of real life.
2. Fear and Anxiety: Some fairy tales involve dark themes, such as violence, death, or evil characters. These elements can be frightening for young children, leading to fear, anxiety, or nightmares.
3. Stereotypes and Gender Roles: Traditional fairy tales often reinforce stereotypes, such as the helpless damsel in distress or the strong, heroic male. This can limit children's understanding of gender roles and contribute to harmful stereotypes.
4. Violence and Aggression: Some fairy tales depict violence, which can desensitize children to aggression or encourage them to view it as a way to solve problems.
5. Materialism: Many fairy tales emphasize wealth, beauty, and social status as indicators of happiness and success. This can foster materialistic values in children, leading them to place undue importance on external possessions.

It's important to note that these are potential drawbacks, and not all children will experience them in the same way. Parents can help mitigate these risks by choosing fairy tales carefully, discussing the themes with their children, and providing a balanced perspective on the world. Additionally, modern fairy tales and adaptations often address these concerns by offering more diverse and inclusive narratives.

Many fairy tales completely negate the suffering that is common to all people. If everyone is living happily once they find their prince, what does that tell young women about how their relationships "should" be? If women are valued for looking pretty and for finding a prince rather than for hard work, resilience, courage and powerful vulnerability, what is that telling our children -sons and daughters -about how women "should" behave and what they "should" focus on? The influence of fairy tales on human gender is also different. From mystery tales, mostly women and young girls are given more emotional emotions. For example, The effects of fairytales on young women are not restricted solely to childhood. Sternberg notes that love stories, such as fairytales, do not only provide a form of entertainment but also serve us a basis for adult assumptions about love. Sternberg states that these fantasy stories provide us with the frame, with which we create our own stories, be they fantasy or not. This means that people's ideal love stories are taken partially from all the love stories they have

read, heard or seen acted out. He notes that whilst these love stories can guide us in our lives they also can lead us down a pathway of many disappointments. This is as most of these stories are unrealistic and when people attempt to practice them in real life they quickly discover to their great disappointment just how unrealistic and unattainable most are. On a similar note, Rowe , as cited in Zipes , states that fairytales seem to exert an imaginative power over the female psyche. Even though most readers take into account that some of the aspects of these stories are obviously elements of fantasy, young women may still be influenced by more subtle ideas by identifying with the heroine in the story. As a result young women subconsciously may transfer some of these subtle ideas from fairytales into real life cultural norms. In addition to this, the traditional patterns and general structure of fairytales adds to the effectiveness of these tales as a source of romantic archetypes and of cultural principles for young women. Rowe also highlights that. Cinderella, Sleeping Beauty, Beauty and the Beast and 'The Frog Prince ' all focus on the important period of adolescence and they sensationalize archetypal female dilemmas and suggest socially acceptable resolutions to these dilemmas. When faced with a dilemma the adolescent girl subconsciously responds to fairytales and gains release from her anxieties by subliminally perceiving in the stories similar dilemmas to the ones she is experiencing. The fact that justice is served at the end and all seems to end on an optimistic note provides the adolescent girl with the feeling that she may deal with her problems as she progresses from childhood to maturity. Besides relieving the psychic fears associated with the rite of passage these fairytales also recommend approved cultural paradigms that ease the adolescent girl's adjustment into the adult community. Lieberman , as cited in Zipes , supports Rowe's arguments by stating that she believes that many women must have formed their psycho-sexual self concepts and ideas of what they can or cannot achieve, what type of behaviour would be rewarded and what kind of reward should be attained, to some extent from their favourite fairytales. These stories have been major influences of the dreams, hopes and fantasies for generations of young women. These dreams, hopes and fantasies are in turn all fuelled by the common desire to fall in love.

Result and Discussion

“If you want your children to be intelligent, read them fairy tales. If you want them to be more intelligent, read them more fairy tales.” Albert Einstein

In fairytales, anything can happen and children learn to think beyond expected boundaries. Learning about faraway lands and different ways to solve problems

can help children develop creative ways of solving their own problems. Fairy tales often have a moral of the story. Stealing is wrong, the good will prevail, don't talk to strangers, don't walk home alone, etc. Children can learn that poor decisions can have negative consequences through such tales. "If you want your children to be intelligent, read them fairy tales. If you want them to be more intelligent, read them more fairy tales." Albert Einstein Fairy tales are many times shared across cultures with slight variations, reading different versions of the same fairy tale help children understand other cultures. Fairy tales also can introduce unknown cultures and customs to children. Having fun reading and enjoying books is one of the first steps in developing a life-long love of reading. When children read stories that they enjoy, they are more likely to like reading and want to read. I truly believe that my love/obsession with fairy tales as a child motivated me to read more challenging novels throughout my school years.

It should also be remembered that there are many negative effects along with positive effects. Magical fairy tales are a genre of literature that often feature fantastical elements, such as magic, mythical creatures, and enchanted lands. These stories typically involve a protagonist who faces challenges and overcomes them with the help of magical forces or beings. While these tales are often seen as children's stories, they can also have profound and complex themes that resonate with adults.

Overcoming Adversity: A common theme in magical fairy tales is the triumph of good over evil. The protagonist often faces significant challenges, such as wicked stepmothers, evil witches, or dangerous creatures. Through their courage, perseverance, and the assistance of magical forces, they are able to overcome these obstacles and achieve their goals.

The Power of Good: Many fairy tales emphasize the importance of kindness, compassion, and honesty. Characters who exhibit these qualities are often rewarded, while those who are selfish or cruel face negative consequences. This reinforces the idea that good actions lead to positive outcomes.

The Journey of Self-Discovery: Fairy tales can also be seen as stories about personal growth and self-discovery. The protagonist often embarks on a journey that leads them to learn about themselves and their place in the world. They may face challenges that test their character and help them to develop important life skills.

The Role of Magic: Magic is a central element of fairy tales and can represent a variety of things. It can symbolize hope, transformation, or the power of the

imagination. Magic can also be a tool for overcoming obstacles and achieving goals that would be impossible in the real world.

Cultural Significance: Fairy tales have been passed down through generations and have become part of the cultural heritage of many societies. They reflect the values, beliefs, and fears of the people who created them.

Psychological Implications: Some scholars argue that fairy tales can have a profound psychological impact on readers. They may help children to process their fears and anxieties, and they can also provide adults with insights into their own lives and experiences.

Literary Techniques: Fairy tales often employ literary devices such as symbolism, metaphor, and allegory. These techniques can add depth and meaning to the story and make it more engaging for readers.

Magical fairy tales are more than just children's stories. They are rich and complex narratives that explore a wide range of themes and can have a lasting impact on readers of all ages. By examining the key themes, results, and cultural significance of these tales, we can gain a deeper appreciation for their enduring appeal.

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